

PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS AND PEDAGOGICAL OBLIGATIONS

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Abstract. In this article, an attempt was made to reveal how a teacher behaves during the lesson, using pedagogical technologies to effectively teach students, and to arouse each student's interest in the lesson. Pedagogical skills are a complex of abilities rich in wisdom and creative reasoning, scientific analysis and fantasy, the ability of a reputable leader who is able to overcome the difficulties of truly scientific education, the ability to feel the soul of students, a skillful and caring approach to the child's personality, whose inner world is delicate and weak.

Key words: Pedagogical skills, intellectual abilities, teacher, student, skills, abilities, sufficient qualifications, knowledge, a qualified specialist, personnel training, pedagogical techniques, thought, character, pedagogical activity, integration, morality, rules, communication, the status of a teacher, active, mind, organization, culture of conversation;

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ НАВЫКИ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОБЯЗАННОСТИ

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Абстрактный. В данной статье предпринята попытка раскрыть способы, с помощью которых учитель может эффективно использовать педагогические технологии для обучения учащихся и пробуждения у каждого ученика интереса к уроку. Педагогическое мастерство – это комплекс способностей, богатых мудростью, научным анализом и воображением, а также умение авторитетного руководства преодолевать трудности подлинно научного образования, чувствовать внутреннее состояние учащихся, умело и бережно подходить к личности ребенка, внутренний мир которого тонок и раним.

Ключевые слова: Педагогическое мастерство, интеллектуальные способности, учитель, ученик, квалификация, умение, достаточная квалификация, знания, зрелый специалист, подготовка кадров, педагогические приемы, мышление, характер, педагогическая деятельность, интеграция, этика, правила, общение, статус учителя, активность, ум, организованность, культура общения;

PEDAGOGIK MAHORAT VA PEDOGOGIK MAJBURIYAT

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola o'qituvchilarning o'quvchilarga dars berish va har bir o'quvchining darsga qiziqishini uyg'otish uchun pedagogik texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanish usullarini ochib

berishga harakat qiladi. Pedagogik mukammallik - bu donolik, ilmiy tahlil va tasavvurga boy qobiliyatlar majmuasi, shuningdek, vakolatli rahbariyatning chinakam ilmiy ta'lim qiyinchiliklarini yengib o'tish, o'quvchilarning ichki holatini tushunish va ichki dunyosi nozik va zaif bo'lgan bolaning shaxsiga mohirona va ehtiyotkorlik bilan yondashish qobiliyatidir.

Kalit so'zlar: Pedagogik mukammallik, intellektual qobiliyatlar, o'qituvchi, o'quvchi, malaka, ko'nikmalar, yetarli malaka, bilim, yetuk mutaxassis, xodimlarni tayyorlash, pedagogik texnikalar, fikrlash, xarakter, pedagogik faoliyat, integratsiya, etika, qoidalar, muloqot, o'qituvchi maqomi, faoliyati, aql-zakovati, tashkilotchiligi, muloqot madaniyati.

Introduction

"Pedagogical skill is the ability to foresee the situation and choose the most effective measures to calm it down." Also, taking into account the personal characteristics of students, their age, family circumstances, and intellectual abilities, their development as fully mature, well-rounded individuals is an integral part of the teacher's pedagogical skill. So, "Pedagogical skill" is the ability to direct the personal, positive activities of students to comprehensive development. Pedagogical skill is mainly manifested in the teacher's activity. In order to achieve pedagogical skill in his/her activity, a teacher must have the ability to generalize, the ability to manage his/her own and students' activities, high knowledge, sufficient qualifications and skills. After our republic gained independence, it was faced with the task of preparing highly qualified specialists who would consciously fight for the development of the republic in a very short period of time, thinking in a new way.

The structure of pedagogical skills. Pedagogical skills include the following components:

- the predominance of humanity in the teacher's work;
- pedagogical talent and ability;
- pedagogical technique (art);
- the teacher's personal aspiration.

Ibn Sina, in his work "Tadbiri Manzil", emphasized the importance of paying attention to the fact that when choosing a teacher for a child, he should pay attention to the fact that he is a truthful, honest, clean, neat and loving person. Each person has the ability to do this or that profession. According to some famous psychologists (F. Gonobolin, N. Kuzmina), the following 6 abilities are important for the teaching profession:

- the ability to get along;
- organization;
- self-control;
- the ability to set goals;
- strength, intelligence;
- a creative approach to activity.

All of this can be included in the pedagogical skills only if it is approached from a humanistic point of view with an educational goal.

Pedagogical technique is considered one of the main parts of pedagogical skills, which allows the teacher to quickly and accurately find the necessary word, tone of speech, look, gesture when dealing with students, to maintain composure in the most acute and unexpected pedagogical situations, and the ability to think clearly and analyze. When exerting a real pedagogical influence, all the skills of the teacher in the field of pedagogical technique are simultaneously evident. Speech, gesture, mimicry, movement are combined. Pedagogical technique is formed on the basis of the individual

psycho-physiological characteristics of the teacher. Individual pedagogical technique also depends on the gender, age, client, character, anatomical and psychological characteristics of the teacher. The level of formation of skills in pedagogical technique to a certain extent reflects the general level of training of the teacher, that is, the pedagogical capabilities of the individual. If the teacher's speech is disorganized, poor, if he is a jerk, has poor taste, and is uncultured, even the most eloquent and correct word will not affect the students, but may lead to the opposite result. That is why the teacher must first of all have been brought up, have ingrained in his blood the culture of sitting and talking in society. Pedagogical activity is the labor activity of people specially trained for this work, who are engaged in educating children who are responsible to the people, the state, and society in order to prepare young people for life, work, and defense of the homeland. The teacher's task of educating a harmonious generation and instilling in them the qualities characteristic of a new person is the most noble, high, and at the same time the most honorable and complex task. Each student has his own behavior and character. It is extremely difficult to take into account and teach these unique characteristics when teaching and educating them. In this, special methods are used that reflect the complexity of social relations between people. The great thinker Abu Ali ibn Sina wrote down his views on pedagogical skills in his works such as "Tadbiri Manzil" and "The Canons of Medicine". For example, in "Tadbiri Manzil", he emphasizes that in order to teach a child, a teacher must be clean, fair, wise, healthy, eloquent and a master of his profession. In "The Canons of Medicine", he addressed issues related to the teacher's speech hygiene. "Shouting loudly for a long time is very dangerous. Because shouting requires a large amount of air to be exhaled (both of which are dangerous)." "In order not to lose your voice and not to exhaust the respiratory system, you should first read in a low voice, and then gradually increase it, but reading in a loud voice should not last long."

Pedagogical activity is the labor activity of people specially trained for this work, who are engaged in educating children who are responsible before the people, the state and society to prepare them for life, work, and defense of the homeland. The teacher's task of raising a harmonious generation and instilling in them the qualities characteristic of a new person is the most noble, high, and at the same time the most honorable and complex task. Each student has his own behavior and character. It is extremely difficult to take into account and teach these unique characteristics when educating and raising them. Special methods are used that reflect the complexity of social relations between people. The great thinker Abu Ali ibn Sino wrote down his views on pedagogical skills in his works such as "Tadbiri Manzil" and "Tib Qanonari". For example, in his work "Tadbiri Manzil", he emphasizes that in order to educate a child, the teacher must be clean, fair, prudent, healthy, eloquent and a master of his profession. In his work "The Laws of Medicine", he addresses issues related to the speech hygiene of the teacher. "Shouting loudly for a long time is very dangerous. Because shouting requires a large amount of air to be exhaled (both of which are dangerous)". "In order not to lose the voice and not to exhaust the respiratory system, it is necessary to first read in a low voice, and then gradually increase it, but reading in a loud voice should not last long."

Communication is a professional tool for a teacher to have an important impact on the student. Teaching is a profession that has existed since the beginning of human history and has always been respected by society and the public.

Pedagogical communication is the creation of a positive, spiritual climate in the classroom during the teacher's interaction with students in the classroom and extracurricular activities. According to Abu

Ali Ibn Sina, "... A teacher should be a person who is strong, conscientious, honest, and well-versed in child-rearing methods and morals. A teacher should be able to study the entire inner and outer world of a student and penetrate the layers of his mind." Pedagogical communication is the creation of a positive psychological environment with students in the classroom and extracurricular activities. Inappropriate, incorrect pedagogical communication causes students to lack self-confidence, speak out of fear, and fear of acting freely. Students learn to fulfill the teacher's wishes as much as possible and act according to his wishes.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Status of a Pedagogue was approved in 2023. According to it, the responsibilities of the educator are strictly defined.

In carrying out his professional activities, the educator must:

- respect the honor, dignity and professional reputation of the participants in the educational process;
- conduct training sessions in accordance with the curriculum and state educational standards;
- take the necessary measures to increase the level of knowledge of students during training sessions;
- use information and communication technologies, advanced and innovative forms and methods of teaching and upbringing;
- take into account the psychological and individual characteristics, physical and mental health, physiological development of students, pay attention to creating conditions for educating individuals with special educational needs and not discriminate against them;
- conduct educational work with minors in cooperation with their parents or other legal representatives;
- regularly improve their qualifications, undergo periodic certification in terms of suitability for the position they hold;
- comply with the charter and (or) other constituent documents of the educational organization, internal labor regulations and pedagogical ethics;
- must undergo a mandatory medical examination on time.

The teacher may also be assigned other obligations in accordance with legislative documents.

Conclusion

A teacher, being a person responsible for the education of a harmonious generation, should not only be an example to those around him with his spiritual and moral culture, but also be able to demonstrate his pedagogical skills, making a worthy contribution to the preparation of qualified personnel as a mature teacher. Possession of pedagogical skills not only provides a basis for the effectiveness of education for a teacher, but also increases his authority in society, and creates respect for students. Organizing practical actions to improve professional skills creates the opportunity to get rid of mistakes made or being made in pedagogical activities, to achieve success in relations with students, colleagues and parents.

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